

Problems and Prospects of Women Entrepreneurship (With Special Reference to Bellary District – Karnataka)

Dr. Rajkumar

Assistant Professor of Commerce, Government College, Autonomous Kalaburagi
Corresponding Author- Dr. Rajkumar

Abstract

The job market scenario in the country will continue to haunt millions of educated and uneducated. Supply will outstrip demand for ages to come. When such is the demand-supply situation, one route that many find rewarding, though there are many hurdles to be overcome is “Entrepreneurship”. A large number of men and women around the world have set up and managed their own business. Entrepreneurship is not new to Indian women. Today women are entering in the field of business in increasing numbers and they do so to face many tangible obstacle. Despite numerous barriers they demonstrate a strong determination to succeed. Women have proved themselves very successful entrepreneurs by engaging in one or two income generating ventures with the confines of their family. They contribute in bringing prosperity to themselves, their family members and to the economy in general. Women owned businesses are becoming increasingly important in the economies of almost all countries. In our country also women are entering into the entrepreneurial career in a big way. At present about 7 per cent of the total enterprises in the country are being run by women. The present paper attempts to highlights the problems faced by the women entrepreneurs in India in general and Belleary district in particular.

Key Words: Development, Problems, Women, Successful, Cultural

Introduction:

“When women moves forward the family moves, the village moves and the nation moves”.

Pundit Jawaharlal Nehru.

Women were made to work, that sentence should be taken literally, not in the metaphorical sense that derives everyday weepies on television. “You are women”, the not-so-subtle message in such programmes goes, “and it is your lot to suffer, be discriminated against and abused, and go through it all with the stoicism of a Zen monk (fine, some fears are allowed)”, women to repeat, were made to work. In all but most strenuous of tasks, where they are at biological disadvantage, they acquit themselves better than their male counterparts.

Consider childbirth by early twenties, a men is physically and mentally equipped to be a mother. Surely that has some bearing on why 22 year old women MBA from any business school is few times as matures as her male batch mate who is still a bit of a boy. In any organization that believes in equal opportunities, the former would be one the fast track to growth and the latter, on the not-so-fast one. Even after making allowances for a 12-18 months maternity break, the women would ahead. That many not have been the case in corporate India. Thus far (except in few companies such as ICICI Bank), but there are signs that things are slowly changing.

Today women are entering in the field of business in increasing numbers and they do so to face many tangible obstacle. Despite numerous barriers they demonstrate a strong determination to succeed. Women have proved themselves very successful entrepreneurs by engaging in one or two

income generating ventures with the confines of their family. They contribute in bringing prosperity to themselves, their family members and to the economy in general. Women owned businesses are becoming increasingly important in the economies of almost all countries. In our country also women are entering into the entrepreneurial career in a big way. At present about 7 per cent of the total enterprises in the country are being run by women.

The need to conduct this study specifically of women’s business ownership is based on the proposition that women problems some of which are in addition to or different from those met by men in starting and running business. In order to find out the problems and constraints being faced by business women, their managerial capabilities and training needs this study was taken up.

The present paper makes an emphasize on the following significant factors of women entrepreneurs;

1. To analyze the role of women as entrepreneur and identify the various avenues for women entrepreneurship.
2. To study the general profile of women entrepreneurs and their enterprises.
3. To find out the problems and constraints being faced by these business women.
4. To find out the managerial capabilities of women entrepreneurs and their training needs.
5. To seek the opinion of respondents regarding certain issues related to women entrepreneurship.

Methodology

Since the study was basically of a descriptive nature, the research instrument for data collection was the interview schedule. The

respondents and the interview schedule were administered personally. A sample of 50 women entrepreneurs was taken according to stratified random sampling technique. The collected data was tabulated and analyzed for drawing the inferences. Due to descriptive nature of the study, statistical hypothesis were not formulated. The analysis in the study was carried out using simple statistical techniques. Inter variables relationships have been established wherever possible by carrying out cross tabulation of the available data. Primary data collected through the questionnaire is analyzed with the use of simple percentage and weighted average methods.

Review of literature

Issues related to women have attracting attention in recent years especially in the contest of social change and economic development. A number of studies have been carried out in the area. A review is made of some of the important works.

One of the major work done in the area of women and development is the book on “Women and social policy”, written by Constantia Safilios Rothschild (1974) she has beautifully presented the theoretical background of social policy related to women.

In a study of “Jamanalal Bajaj Institute of Management studies” University of Mumbai 1976, an effort has been made to study the social and business implications of women managers entering the business scheme in India.

Lalitha devi in her study (1982) has tried to show that employment percentage against age, education, family type, place of residence plays a crucial role in raising the status of women.

Study conducted by Rajasthan entrepreneurs in 1983 brings out the point that women are equally effective as men in business industry’

Dr. Anali Mehta has made a study on “Women entrepreneurship in Gujarat” (1993). According to her study the women entrepreneurs appreciated the training programmes conducted by centre for entrepreneurship development (CED) but were little unhappy about the lack of substantial follow up action.

A research study (1993) in USA found that banks and financial institutions historically viewed that women entrepreneur as more doubtful propositions than men often discriminating subtly or overtly in bending practices.

A research study entitled “Entrepreneurial competition and gender wise variations” (1994) discussed the concept of entrepreneurial competencies as determinants of entrepreneurial development. The finding conclusively that gender therefore may not be the determinant of competence levels in twin entrepreneur success.

An exploratory research study on “women entrepreneurs in transition (1994) identified five transitions in women entrepreneurs based on analysis of 150 cases of women entrepreneurs in India despite predicting the future trends.

An empirical study on “emerging profile of small women entrepreneurs – cum – managers in India a case study” revealed that women entrepreneurs in India engaged in died variety of non-traditional business activities are well equipped with education and experience and are highly motivated to their business independently and are prepared to face any challenge. They are fully involved in the business so as to gain and enhance economic and social status.

Dr. Hanumant Yadav, in his research paper “Problem of Women Entrepreneurship in Eastern Madhya Pradesh” (1998) revealed that the paucity of funds is the cruse of all the problems. If it is solved half of the major problems are solved.

Need for the study

It is evident from the preceding brief review of literature that issues related to women have been attracting attention in recent years especially in the context of social and economic development. Therefore, on account of their importance, studies on women entrepreneurship have been carried out (or) are in the process in almost every economy. A few studies that are available are mostly surveys of economic aspects and of problems of running the industrial units. Many of these are also related or conducted in metropolitan or urban areas. There are no previous studies that constraints data on prospect of women entrepreneurship in a backward area like Bellary District in Karnataka has been undertaken. Therefore, it has incited us to undertake the study.

Limitation of the study

The study is not free from the certain limitations. This study is limited only to women entrepreneurs of Bellary District of Karnataka, has been chosen for the purpose of the study due to time and resource constraint.

As the questionnaire covers various aspects of the study, the respondents may not be able to answer certain questions, many of them have given poor response to questionnaire it is very difficult to present the exact information from their memory.

Conclusion and projection in some cases are to be based on the researcher’s own judgment. Therefore, the personal limitations of the researcher need special mention.

Need for Women Entrepreneurship

The emergence of women entrepreneurs in a society depends to a great extent on the economic, religious, cultural, social, psychological and other factors. Hence, the emergence of women

as entrepreneurs in India should be seen as a resurgence of the rightfully respectable socio-economic status of women. However, a society constrained by suppressive socio-economic factors cannot generate the much needed women entrepreneurs on its own. The women were not given regained scope for education in the country. The private initiatives directed towards the growth of entrepreneurs as existing in USA and in UK are not wide spread in our country. Moreover, women have become the integral part of the industrialized society.

Women are expected to come out from tradition by taking up self employment ventures. The liberalization policy of the government has thrown-up to open a vast area of the economy for private entrepreneurship under such circumstances special efforts to develop women entrepreneurship is keenly felt. A very few women entrepreneurs have had successful in their venture having different background in the Indian corporate world they are Ekta Kapoor (creative director of Balaji Tlifilms), Kiran Mazumadar Shaw (fonder and director of Biocon Groups), Anu Aga (chairperson,

Thermax), Lalita Gupte (Joint M.D ICICI Bank), Renu Karnad (Executive Director HDFC), Naina Kidwailal (Deputy CEO, HSBC) etc.

Socio-Economic Conditions of Women Entrepreneurs

An entrepreneur's works as an investor, promoter, organizer, manager, coordinator and also a capitalized she takes decisions with regard to work inside the house, the some would be extended in the work place. Findings of the study under taken by Shanta Kholi Chandra reveals that socio-economic factor are affecting the women entrepreneurs. In her study majorities of women entrepreneurs are young, and do not belong to business families. Marital status and family bindings in majority of the cases did not interfere significant in continuing the enterprise.

Period of Establishment

The numbers of enterprises established by women entrepreneurs in Bellary district are very less being it is a backward area, less literacy rate, and are also not financially sound, very few women entrepreneurs are there. Even among them very few women entrepreneurs are successful.

Table-1
Number of enterprises established by women entrepreneurs

Sl. No.	Year of establishment	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Below 1970	2	8
2.	1970 – 1980	1	4
3.	1980-1990	2	8
4.	1990-2000	15	60
5.	2000-2001	2	8
6.	2001-2002	3	12
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The critical evaluation of the above table reveals that, there is a greater variation among male and female entrepreneurs towards the establishment of entrepreneurs towards the establishment of

enterprises. Not even 8 per cent has been covered towards enterprises established by women enterprises in Bellary district in 2000-2001.

Table-2
Age wise classification of respondents

Sl. No.	Age	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	10-20	2	8
2.	20-30	11	44
3.	30-40	7	28
4.	40-50	2	8
5.	50-60	2	8
6.	Above – 60	1	4
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

It can be evident from the above table-2 out of the 11 women entrepreneurs in Bellary district of the women entrepreneurs belong to the age group of 20-30 years, in second position 28 per

cent women entrepreneurs belong to 30-40 age groups in study area. In third position 8 per cent of women entrepreneurs belong to below 20 years age group and same percent of women entrepreneurs

were also belonged to 40-50 age groups and 50-60 age groups. Most of the women entrepreneurs are

middle age; this group attains some maturity to settle in the field of entrepreneurship.

Table -3
Level of education

Sl. No.	Education level	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Illiteracy	3	12
2.	1-10	13	52
3.	10-12	2	8
4.	12-15	4	16
5.	15-17	1	4
6.	Professional	2	8
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

It is clear from the above table-3 education wise analysis shows that most of the women entrepreneurs are in below graduation level. Being the district is in backward region even some women entrepreneurs are there with no education.

Some women entrepreneurs are expert in technical field. In Bellary district majority of the women are in High School Level (52%) and in the case of second place is Degree level (16%) and third place is illiteracy of women entrepreneurs i.e., (12%).

Table-4
Religion and Cast wise Distribution

Sl. No.	Caste	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Scheduled caste	3	12
2.	Scheduled tribe	1	4
3.	Backward caste	17	68
4.	Other caste	4	16
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

Above table-4 reveals that among the women entrepreneurs covered by the sample study are belonged to different casts, caste and religion has also placed a significant role in

entrepreneurship development. 68 per cent of sample sizes are belonged to backward caste, SC and ST women entrepreneurs are few in numbers i.e., 12 per cent and 4 per cent respectively.

Table-5
Religion wise Distribution

Sl. No.	Religion	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Hindu	23	92
2.	Muslim	2	8
3.	Christian	-	-
4.	Others	-	-
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

It is clear from the above table that most of the women entrepreneurs belong to other backward classes category and non-reserved class. Among the

women entrepreneurs covered by the sample study 92 per cent were belonged to Hindu in Bellary district and rest of 8 per cent belonged to Muslims.

Table-6
Marital status

Sl. No.	Particular	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Unmarried	4	16
2.	Married	21	84
3.	Windows	-	-

Total	25	100
--------------	-----------	------------

Source: Field investigation

Martial status of women entrepreneurs will also have an influence towards the success of enterprise. It is clear from the above table that 16 per cent women entrepreneurs are unmarried and

remaining 84 per cent women entrepreneurs in Bellary district were married. They are all running the enterprise with the help of their family member.

Table -7
Type of family

Sl. No.	Family type	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Joint family	7	28
2.	Nuclear family	18	72
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

Type of family will play a significant role in the development of women entrepreneurs. It is clear from the above table that majority of women entrepreneurs are living in nuclear family and they are managing the enterprises very easily. Table 3 shows that it shows that 72 per cent of the women

entrepreneurs in Bellary district belong to nuclear family and rest of respondents belonged to joint family. It indicates that to manage the business successfully nuclear family environment is more favourable for the women entrepreneurs.

Table- 8: Family background

Sl. No.	Family Background	Total	
		No. of women Entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Agriculture	12	48
2.	Business	9	36
3.	Industry	1	4
4.	Services	2	8
5.	Others	1	4
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The family background of women entrepreneurs will play an important role for the development of women entrepreneurship. It is clear from the above table that most of the family members of the women entrepreneurs are from the agriculture background. In Bellary district it stood at 48 per cent. It emphasizes the fact that a family

background of agriculture experience influence to a greater degree in taking to entrepreneurship as a career. Business environment in the family, encouragement and support from the family members, and at some times situational forces all has combined for the women entrepreneurs in setting up of an enterprise.

Table – 9: Type of the Enterprise

Sl. No.	Type of enterprise	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Manufacturing	16	64
2.	Job working	2	8
3.	Servicing	4	16
4.	Assembling	1	4
5.	Sub-contracting	2	8
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

A study has also been carried out to know about the type of the enterprise, which the women entrepreneurs are carrying out. The above table reveals that most of the women entrepreneurs were in manufacturing sector in Bellary district (64%).

Servicing here refers being in the business of Beauty parlor, tailoring, hotels, computer centre etc. In second place is servicing sector in Bellary district with 16 per cent of sample group.

Table-10: Age of the enterprise

Sl. No.	Period of establishment	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	1-5	14	56
2.	5-10	7	28
3.	10-15	2	8
4.	Above 15	2	8
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The critical evaluation of above table portraits that most of the enterprises i.e., 56 per cent of sample size are having age of the enterprise in between 1-5 years of age and 28 per cent are in between 5-10 years of age.

Table-11: Ownership of the firm

Sl. No.	Type of enterprises	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Proprietorship	16	64
2.	Partnership	6	24
3.	Co-operatives	1	4
4.	Private limited	1	4
5.	Public limited	1	4
6.	Others	-	0
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The above table indicates that the majority of units are sole proprietorship units. A sole trader is one who carries as the business by her self and sharing profit and losses individually and bearing unlimited liabilities, some are the units were found in private limited and public limited company and co-operative form of organization in the survey taken from the women entrepreneurs of Bellary district.

Table-12: Location of the entrepreneurs

Sl. No.	Location of the entrepreneurs	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Urban	16	64
2.	Semi-urban	4	16
3.	Rural	5	20
Total		25	100

Source: Field Investigation

It is clear from the above table that most of the women entrepreneurs belong to the urban area (64%). It shows the higher awareness among the women of the urban area towards entrepreneurship. There are so many factors for the less awareness in rural areas, for example lack of education, lack of proper guidance, lack of required information about the business, facilities and services available, orthodox social with religious environment working as subsidiary in the agriculture etc.

Table -13: Period of working days

Sl. No.	Period of working days	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Regular	19	76
2.	Seasonal	6	24
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

There are certain industries where it works in only seasonal periods for example in case of papad industries, the season is between December – May during that period only the processing of papad industry takes place. It is evident from the above table that majority of the units i.e., 76 per cent were regular in nature. Regular units such as tailoring, beauty parlor, computer center, hotel, embroidering etc., and rest of 24 per cent carry their business on seasonal basis.

Table-14: Size of total investment

Sl. No.	Size of investment (in Rs.)	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	1,000 to 10,000	14	56
2.	10,000 to 50,000	7	28
3.	50,000 to 1,00,000	2	8
4.	1,00,000 to 5,00,000	1	4
5.	Above 5,00,000	1	4
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The above table shows that almost 92 per cent of the units are having an investment of below Rs. 1 lakh, being very backward region women were not well equipped for which women entrepreneurs will start small scale industries, in case of tailoring, embroidering, hotel, papad

industries the investment required is less. Even in Xerox centers and beauty parlour initial investment is less. This shows the initial capacity and the standard of women entrepreneurs in Bellary district was very poor.

Table-15: Type of women entrepreneurs in Bellary district

Sl. No.	Types of work	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Tailoring	7	28
2.	Beauty parloru	2	8
3.	Hand pumps	1	4
4.	Garments	2	8
5.	Ophthalmologist/clinic	1	4
6.	Computer	1	4
7.	Papad industry	2	8
8.	Self employment	3	12
9.	Hotel	1	4
10.	Department store	1	4
11.	Painting and embroidering	1	4
12.	General fancy	-	-
13.	Bangle store	1	4
14.	Agarbatti	-	-
15.	Bakery	1	4
16.	Herbal production	-	-
17.	Beauty care	1	4
18.	Flour mill	-	-
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The areas selected by women entrepreneurs toward their venture differ from women to women and also from place to place moreover, it depends upon the financial capacity, educational background etc. It shows that the women are not economically sound and are not

well educated. They even do not posses the technical skills. As Bellary district is a backward district. 28 per cent of sample size is engaged in tailoring and 1per cent of sample group are engaged in garment, hotel and agarbatti business etc.

Table-16: Training and experience of women entrepreneurs

Sl. No.	Trained/untrained women entrepreneurs	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Trained women entrepreneurs	23	92
2.	Untrained women entrepreneurs	2	8
Total		25	100

Source: Field Investigation

The above table shows that more percentage of women entrepreneurs has undergone training for the women entrepreneurs in Bellary district as given by District Industries Centre (DIC) and Syndicate Institute of Rural Development (SIRD) to start. Beauty parlor, computer centres, tailoring and other business. 92 per cent of sample size undergone training and only 8 per cent of sample size are untrained.

Influencing Factors of Women Entrepreneurs

Motivational or influencing factor plays a predominant role in starting the enterprise. There may be internal factors and external factors which motivate women entrepreneurs to start business. External factors are government, societies, family members, relatives and friends.

Each respondent was asked to pick and rank them according to the importance she attached to each of the reasons mentioned by her is shown in below table.

Table 17
Source of media about this business

Sl. No.	Sources of media about this business	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Government	6	24
2.	Societies	2	8
3.	Electric media	1	4
4.	Print medias	1	4
5.	Fiends and relatives	14	56
6.	Others	2	8
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

Most of the women entrepreneurs selected for the study 58% of sample size agreed that they have got sufficient support and co-operation from their family whether they belong to nuclear family or joint family. This indicates the importance of influencing factor of family co-operation for the development of women entrepreneurship.

Government acquires second importance with the weighted score of 24 points in Bellary

district. Others ranked third with the weighted score in Bellary district.

An attempt has also been made in this regard by examining the important internal motivational factor influencing on women to establish enterprise viz. professional, by birth, economic profit, to be economically independent, to do something to till time, its my hobbies and to do social service.

Table -18: Reason for starring this business

Sl. No.	Reasons for this business	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Professional	3	12
2.	By birth	1	4
3.	Earning profit	11	44
4.	To be economical independent	2	8
5.	To do something worth	1	4
6.	Its my hobbies	1	4
7.	To do social service	5	20
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

The above table indicates that the prominent factors which are encouraged the women entrepreneurs to start the enterprise in Bellary district. "Economic profit" has been the prime motivation or influencing factor which acquires to top most importance with the weighted score of 44 in Bellary district.

Utilization of capital resources of the family stood second position. As explained earlier,

family will play a predominant role in influencing the women entrepreneurs, some women entrepreneurs want to fulfill their own ambition. This will also play an influencing factor for starring the enterprise.

The third influencing factor which makes women entrepreneurs to start the enterprise is awareness about the idea of starting the enterprise.

Table-19: Source of Information

Sl. No.	Come to know about this business	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Government	6	24
2.	Societies	1	4
3.	Electronic medias	1	4
4.	Print medias	1	4
5.	Friends and relatives	14	56
6.	Others	2	8
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

Source of awareness for the largest single group were advice from friends and relatives with the weighted score of 56 points, the next most important reason was visit to similar DIC in the district with the weighted score of 24 points and others in a similar unit ranked as third reason for starting a industrial.

Location Factors

In an attempt to study the location factors that influence the women entrepreneurs in starting up their venture. Seven factors were identified by 25 women entrepreneurs in Bellary district and each women entrepreneurs was asked to indicate three factors that were most encouraging to her in the order of priority in starting her unit.

Table 20: Locational factors in Bellary district

Sl. No.	Kind of assistance/help you require	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Incentive from government	-	-
2.	Subsidized loan	13	52
3.	Interest free loan	2	8
4.	Raw material supply at concessional rate	1	4
5.	Purchase of finished product by government	1	4
6.	Easy finance / loans on bank and financial institution	4	16
7.	Protection of small women entrepreneurs	4	16
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

Subsidized loans were perceived as the most encouraging factor among 13 entrepreneurs. The next most encouraging factor was protection of small women entrepreneurs, followed by easy finance/loans by bank and financial institutions.

Problems in Women Entrepreneurs

The new thrust given to the process of economic development of the country by the new dynamic leadership has created an all round enthusiasm and the new slogan of “March towards the 21st century” has gained popularity, but in this new enthusiasm towards the economic development of the country is not given much attention as required and that sector is women entrepreneurs.

The biggest problem against a women entrepreneur is that she is a women. Its means that the attitude of society towards women and constraints in which she has to live and works is quite address. Women are still suffering from male reservations. These reservations create difficulties and problems at all level i.e., family support, training, financial licensing and marketing women in non-urban areas have to suffer still further.

The following table shows the factors that inhibited women entrepreneurs or the problems faced by women entrepreneurs in the process of starting the unit in Bellary district.

Table-21: Discouraging factors in Bellary district

Sl. No.	Problems / discouraging factor	Total	
		No. of women entrepreneurs	Percentage
1.	Competition	14	57
2.	Price fluctuation	3	12
3.	Irregular supply of raw materials	2	9
4.	Storage	-	-
5.	Bargaining	1	2
6.	Fluctuation in demand	2	9
7.	Lack of experience	1	3
8.	Lack of technical know how	1	6
9.	Capital shortage	1	2
Total		25	100

Source: Field investigation

From the above table it can be noted that competition came out as the most influencing factor by the entire respondent (25 respondents in Bellary district) concerned.

The second highest problem by women entrepreneurs is price fluctuation in district. Third highest problem faced by women entrepreneurs in Bellary district, is irregularly supply of raw materials and fluctuation in demand for certain industries such as cloths, beauty creams, electricity facility and raw materials is important to produce the ultimate product.

Another important problem face by women entrepreneurs was in relation to lack of technical know how, it plays very predominant role in the development of woman entrepreneurs and also enterprise.

Even from the above table it can be observed that “competition was biggest problem faced by women entrepreneurs, it might be either from male entrepreneurs or from fellow entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs cited interest to do businesses as the main reason behind their planning into the entrepreneur’s world. Some of these said that business was in their blood and they have a love for business profession. The other problems faced by women entrepreneurs are as follows:

1. Lack of suitable and appropriate environment for promotion of entrepreneurship.
2. Lack of confidence to start their venture
3. Social pressure and attitude of debuting a women’s capability
4. Inadequate involvement of financial and other agencies to assist women to tackle problems that of finance etc.

Conclusion

Finally it can be concluded that, the women entrepreneurs must accept all the challenges and should overcome with her enthusiasm and confidence in herself. In a study

made in Bellary district most of the women entrepreneurs are managing their business simply without any urge to expand, develop or grow the enterprise, they are managing business in a traditional way since a long time, they do not even bother to change their technology of production and even the way of marketing of the product. They are satisfied only with their existing system, such an attitude on the part of any entrepreneurs is not desirable. The business world moving ahead in all aspects in the midst of cut throughout competition at national and international level.

References

1. Airken Huge, J. “Explorations in Enterprise” Ed. Harward University Press, Cambridge, 1965, P. 46.
2. Anitha Sharma, “Modernization and station of working women in India,” Mittal publications, New Delhi, 1990.
3. Bhanushah, S. G. “Entrepreneurship Development”, Himalaya Publishing House, 1981, Bombay.
4. Chandra Shantha Kohli, “Development of women in India,” Shakti Books, Delhi.
5. Devendra “Status and position of women in India”, Shakti Books, Delhi.
6. Gosavi, M. S. “Business education and entrepreneurs development”, Ed. Gokhale education society’s publication, Nasik, 1986.
7. Gupta Ashish “Indian Entrepreneurs culture”. Vishwas Prakasha, U. K., 1994.
8. Anjali Metha, “ A study an women entrepreneurs in Gujarat”, Summary published in Times of India,” Ahmedabad, 8 December, 1993.
9. Patel, V. G., “Entrepreneurs are not born”, Economic Times, December 21, August, 1991.
10. Tinani Madan, “Women Entrepreneurs”, - an article published in the Economic times”, 10th April 1998.